

The Theorem of the Formula of Speed of Light, Instead of $E=Mc^2$, $E=Mm^2$ is Most Important for Scholars and Scientists in Science, in Very Simple Language

Dhananjay Shantaram Janorkar

Author, Researcher and Founder President,
Shantaram Janorkar Foundation of Mathematics,
Mahan - 444405, Tq. Barshitakli, Dist. Akola,
(Maharashtra State), INDIA
sjfomindia1@gmail.com

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Abstract

I give here geometrical method of determination of the new formula of speed of light in Very Simple Language. New formula of speed of light is $E=Mm^2$ Which means Energy = Mass x (Speed of Mass)², There is an addition in this theorem so the speed of light is according to the rules of mathematics. It is also according to the rules of speed.

Keywords

Geometrical method; The speed of the source of light; The speed of mass; The speed of the cosmos; The speed of light; Doubt; The new formula of speed of light is $E=Mm^2$ which means Energy = Mass x (Speed of Mass)²; Absolute speed; Relative speed, The speed of light is 186000 miles/second it has been accepted by scientists; The speed of light i. e. 186000 miles/second is of the source of light in the formula $E=Mm^2$.

I. INTRODUCTION

I give here geometrical method of determination of the new formula of speed of light in Very Simple Language. New formula of speed of light is $E=Mm^2$ Which means Energy = Mass x (Speed of Mass)², There is an addition in this theorem so the speed of light is according to the rules of mathematics. It is also according to the rules of speed. By giving various examples in this research paper, I have tried to explain these formulae in scientific and mathematical language.

In Geometry, symbol for measurement accepted by world scientists (world official) is degree and the very degree is the root, scale, source and base of the research. Degree: Closed chop (Compass), Tip of the compass means point, means 1 point, means 1° degree, means dot • = degree means unit of measurement. The base of this whole research is 36° measure of circle.

II. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

$E=Mm^2$ This Formula of Speed of Light is Most Important for Scholars and Scientists in Science, in Very Simple Language

The construction of formula:

The feature of this construction is that no algebraic and geometrical formulae are involved in it. The construction of the geometry is smooth, simple and bears symmetry. The value of the *circumference of a circle* is calculated by assigning values to the radius and arc radius created in the construction. It is also a feature of using the geometry construction to calculate *the speed of mass and the speed of light*.

The Speed of Mass:

Diagram No.1

The addition of speeds: 46,500 multiple two OR 46,500 plus 46,500 (two interior centers of circle in the interior of original circle) we get inner speed *outcomes 93,000 mile/second*.

The addition of speeds: 46,500 multiple four (four outside centers of circle in the outside of original circle) we gets outside speed, the speed of mass *outcomes 1,86,000 mile/ second*. By giving examples various types of methods.

Instead of $E=Mc^2$ which means Energy = Mass x (Speed of light 1,86,000 miles/second)²,

$E=Mm^2$ which means Energy = Mass x (Speed of Mass 1,86,000 miles/second)²

Speed of Light > Is greater than the Speed of Mass

The Speed of Light:

Speed of Mass (1, 86,000 miles/second) × Measure of centre of circle on the circumference of circle of the construction (6° six degree) × Measure of circumference outside of the circle (10⁴ Ten to the power four) × Measure of centre of circle interior of the circle (2 two) we gets speed of light **22,32,00,00,000 mile/ second** (twenty two hundred and thirty two crore miles per second).

The speed of light is absolute or relative:

The second doubt is that, is the speed of light **exceptional absolute**? We clear this doubt by the following explanation:

Diagram No. 2

This speed 1,86,000 miles/second is of mass and not of light. This speed is not absolute but it is relative. This speed is not exceptional to the rule of speed. See the side diagram. This diagram is that of a “Solid Sphere”. There are in total seven centres of circle which include, the original circle, six measure of centre of six circles on the circumference of circle, one centre point of the original circle + six centre points of six circle, Thus there are seven centre of circle in total. But due to the cube number of this is increased. It is as follows: One (1) centre point of the sphere + Eight (8) vertex of the cube means eight centre points of the circle thus in total nine (9) centre of circle can be sighted.

Centre of Sphere + Eight Vertices of Cube, namely, Eight Centre Points of Circle = 9 Centre Points
 $1 + 8 = 9$ Centre Points

If these 9 centre points are multiplied by 10^4 , we get the speed of the cosmos.

$9 \times 10^4 = 9 \times 10 \times 10 \times 10 \times 10 = 90,000$ miles/second speed

The speed, 90, 000 miles/second is attributed to the cosmos. As proved by the physicists, the ultimate cosmos at the distance of six (6) are expanding or running with this speed.

The cosmos are running in opposite directions

← 90,000 + 90,000 → The addition of speeds

The speed of explosion, namely, the speed of cosmos is 1, 80,000. It means that if the six (6) partial circle centers are multiplied by 10^3 we get the “self-speed” of the cosmos.

$6 \times 10^3 = 6 \times 10 \times 10 \times 10 = 6,000$ miles/second is the self-speed of the cosmos.

Speed of Explosion	+	Self-Speed	=	Total Speed
1,80,000	+	6,000	=	1,86,000 mile/second speed

Here, the additions of speed is carried out, hence the speed, 1,86,000 mile/second is not absolute speed but it is relative speed and as it obeys the laws of mathematics, it is not exceptional. It has been proved. Here the second doubt has been cleared.

Absolute Speed: Speed tells how fast an object is moving without saying anything about its direction. Speed is always positive. Speed is the "absolute value" of the velocity. Speed in the velocity information without the sign or direction information.

Relative Speed: Relative speed is defined as the speed of a moving object with respect to another. When two objects are moving in the same direction, relative speed is calculated as their difference. When the two objects are moving in opposite directions, relative speed is computed by adding the two speeds.

The formula, $E = Mc^2$ was discovered by the great scientist, Albert Einstein. We all know this Energy = mass x the square of the speed of light.

The speed of light is exceptional. The speed of light is the same everywhere. There is no difference in it and it assumed to be 1, 86,000 miles/second or 3, 00,000 km/s.

Whatever the source of light is, the speed of it is the same. And it is only 1,86,000 miles/second or 3,00,000 km/s. Till the research carried out so far, no matter has found to be travelling with more speed than the light. Therefore, the speed of the light is assumed to be the highest. *The speed of light is not relative but it is absolute. It was also proved by Einstein.* Einstein’s principle of relativism is based on the axiom that “nothing can surpass the speed of light.”

Doubt

1) Does the speed of light, i. e., 1, 86,000 miles/second given by Albert Einstein really belong to light?

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Answer: In this research paper it has been proved that the speed 1, 86,000 miles/per second is attributed to mass and not to light. The speed of light is 22,32,00,00,000 miles/second (two thousand two hundred and thirty two cores miles/second). Here the first doubt has been cleared.

2) Is the speed of light exceptional, absolute?

Answer: The additions of speed is carried out, hence the speed, 1, 86,000 mile/second is not absolute speed but it is relative speed and as it obeys the laws of mathematics, it is not exceptional. It has been proved. Here the second doubt has been cleared.

These two doubts arise. The explanation of the same is given in this research paper in scientific and mathematical language. The new formula for power is $E = Mm^2$, i., e. Power = mass x square of the speed of mass. The speed of light is proved to be 22,32,00,00,000 miles/second (two thousand two hundred and thirty two cores miles/second). In the formula, $E = Mm^2$, **E** stands for **power or energy**, **M** for **mass** and **m²** for **the square of speed of mass** and as there is an addition of speeds in this formula, therefore the speed of light is in accordance with the rules of mathematics. It is also in accordance with the rules of speed. It was proved by my father Late Mr. Shantaram Bapurao Janorkar. In Geometry, symbol for measurement accepted by world scientists (world official) is degree and this degree is the root, scale, source and base of the research. Degree: Closed chop (Compass), Tip of the compass means point, means 1 point, means 1° degree, means dot • = degree means unit of measurement. The base of this whole research is 36° measure of circle.

III. CONCLUSIONS

1. Mathematics (Geometrical) method it is a good method for determination of the formula of speed of light.
2. The new formula of speed of light is $E=Mm^2$ which means Energy = Mass x (Speed of Mass) ².
3. 1,86,000 miles/per second, This speed of mass is according to the rules of speed. It means that speed is relative.
4. The Speed of Light/per second = 22,32,00,00,000 mile most greatest speed. (The Speed of Light is twenty two hundred and thirty two crore miles per second).
5. The additions of speed is carried out, hence the speed of light according to the rules of mathematics. Therefore, it is relative.
6. It is also a feature of using the geometry construction to calculate *the speed of mass and the speed of light*.

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Note * *Mul sanshodhan paper hee Marathi Bhashemadhe Aahet ($E = Mc^2$, Cya Aivaji $E = Mm^2$ Ha Prakash Vegachya Sutracha Siddhanta Vidnyanatil Skolars Aani Shastradnyannasathi Sarvat Mahattvacha, Agadi Sopya Bhaset), (In Marathi).*
(The Original Research Papers are in Marathi Language).

Researcher and Author

Mr. Dhananjay Shantaram Janorkar,
Mahan, Tq. Barshitakali, Dist. Akola,
(Maharashtra State), INDIA
Contact: + 91 - 9021607450, 9226442256
E-mail: sjfomindia@gmail.com, dsjanorkar@gmail.com
www.sbjankar.com

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